

Effectiveness of Online Teaching Pedagogy on Learners

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Abstract:- This study investigated a set of prescribed methods, strategies, and practices for teaching academic subjects in an online (or blended) environment, where students are in a physical location separate from the faculty member and other students. Online pedagogy is useful for the learner because utilizing the positive aspects of technology so that online teacher can provide a quality educational learning experience. Online pedagogy is to help learners earn higher education no matter where they are located. Learners can also learn what approaches work best for them, which learning activities, learning styles, and how to develop concepts and build mental models to further their learning. Learner's language, competence and motivation were examined within a socio educational framework. The key benefits of online pedagogy are low costs, no traveling required, self-paced coursework, and time flexibility. In this paper the literature survey is focused on effect of online pedagogy on the learners and how much quality knowledge can gain from the online pedagogy.

Keywords:- Evaluation, Pedagogy, Competence, Motivation, Framework, Flexibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

[1]. For the last five years, online training offers have significantly improved the education sector. That each school would be offering teacher-led online classes both in combination and remotely to give all learners individual opportunities to fulfil their needs pedagogical. Professors are a key component of online study. However, the skills for efficient online instruction go beyond the skills for good teaching in the classroom. To adapt to the simulated world, online instructors must be prepared to adjust the teaching practice and pedagogic approaches used in conventional environments, with a major function being to promote student engagement and collaboration.

Online learning has contributed to the education sector by offering flexible and creative innovative alternatives for learners [2]. Sometimes find the separate areas for growth in combined learning and additional online courses does not inherently imply a "distance" learning for learners and teachers. Online supplementary programs, teachers, learners, and others interested in physical education will receive online classes, although mixed learning options are partially offered in online and partly face-to-face. The absence of connections to classes, a shortage of professional instructors,

growing learner groups, and a restricted area and contradictions of course planning offer online teaching with opportunities to meet voids that school system districts find challenging to solve [3]. It is a way of offering a wide range of courses from basic subjects to students' choices, especially in small-scale schools and rural and urban areas [4].

For several factors, the distribution of online courses may be suggested. Over everything, attention should be paid to the interests of learners.[5] Many educational establishments are already changing their students' demographics. The several seminaries no longer consider the twenty-one-year-old white male to be their average people. The learner is always older, accepts secondary education, and would be like a female as male as in many instances. Today, students at the seminary experience dynamic lives and sometimes want to combine college, family responsibilities, church service, and part-time work. It is always wonder at our students' dedication to a religious curriculum and respect it. The removal of a long journey by introducing certain online courses will free some student's priceless time. The timetable, therefore, provides a great deal of versatility and a bonus for residential students. It is inconceivable that people graduate with online teacher training programs but most conventional and alternative teacher education programs, according to Jung and NEA, do not train learners for online learning. It may be seen that people graduate with online teaching education programs.

Online pedagogy offering online classes recruiting new students in unused markets. Many seminars have difficulty with falling enrolments and new entrants can be attracted by online courses. Most religious organizations also do not implement complete services online. However, one or two distance courses are offered for novice entrants, maybe after years of formal study, to learn theology and assess their intellectual skills. One believes the experience would be sufficiently good to participate in the full program. So here is a word of warning. The advantage of providing online instruction is new recruiting, but not the only reason for delivering online courses.

The sharing of online courses facilitates innovative pedagogy for learners and faculty. Learners learn how to construct themselves and teachers how to teach differently. Whatever you do in training, at least for reflective practitioners, there is still something to understand. True strategies will no longer be effective and modern contexts

need new approaches. In committing itself to teach online, faculty would certainly have its learning curve, not so much in technical terms as in teaching. To optimize the pedagogic ability of the online world, one needs to plan a course. However, the depressing first news is delivery of online courses would not fix the financial problems of an organization. The courses should only cost a minimum of desperately planned and poorly executed. They could not support themselves for the long term though generating an initial surplus revenue. Online distribution of quality courses is costly and particularly when an organization must invest in technical infrastructure. Even if the campus is cabled with digital lines and machines are on each desk, the consistency of internet distribution is nevertheless substantial. The faculty would notice that online training will at first be very arduous and its usual workload. Although several encounters have been quite satisfied, organizations ought to examine what kinds of fair professional incentives may be needed to maintain quality online curriculum development (e.g., reduced teaching load, and extra pay).

There is also a growing variety of Advanced Placement (A.P.) or university courses eligible for high school students. Online learning offers an additional solution to children that cannot operate through a specified educational program for several purposes, e.g. risky students, professional athletes and students, dropouts, pregnant or imprisoned students. There are performed in response to a semi-annual, experiential online course designed to expose educators to online teaching at a university in India. The study aimed to analyze the educational experiences of preservation teacher education when learning to be taught online and thereby add to an ongoing online pedagogical conversation.

However, the institution will profit from the execution of the online course properly. It not only helps the institution to fulfil its mission to provide quality education but also enables niche marketing. The college or a staff member that might be less enrolling would be given courses that may have an interest in the campus. For instance, Queen's Theological College has successfully offered a fourth-semester course online in the past few years in India. Any individuals carrying out an ordained service in India must follow this path. Although some of our students attend online classes, it also attracts students who are ordained in other Indian universities and people who are looking to join the department formally in India. If they would sell this course on-campus only, it has a much wider online market.

II. BENEFITS OF PEDAGOGY

➤ *Educational Benefit*

The advantage of students learning more than the substance of a course is typical in online classes. Weiner observed that online schooling in Cyber Schools in India greatly increased writing and computing skills. This research reveals that motivational questions and highly organized courses are the secret of good online learning for teenage learners. The study also shows that young learners are prepared to learn in cyberspace, if they will contribute to

their education and if they, particularly their professors, receive adequate assistance and guidance.

➤ *Economic Benefits*

Cost is the tenured faculty's multipound tool. Before incorporating online learning programs, the faculty must consider several expense considerations. By building matrices for online learning prices, Bartley and Olgren studied cost considerations.[7] They showed the cost drivers separated into the cost of capital and recurring costs of manufacturing, distribution, fluctuating, and fixed costs. The cost of capital is machinery or inventory procurement prices. Recent charges are continuously incurred costs (for example, the cost of computer support). Production costs are those linked to the program/course creation, while distribution costs are the costs related to the delivery or 'teaching' of materials. Bartley concluded after weighing the pros and cons of online learning that the advantages of online learning are rather real and that any more costs for the school gains can be justified. Huge returns from online courses are expected by universities. Based on an inquiry carried out in Nigeria, an accessible and distance learning institution has been concluded to be extremely cost-effective in considering the establishment objective in the general context of the education sector. Distance training programs have been considered expensive at the first level and are increasingly cheaper because of economies of scale [7]. Online learning is providing more promising synchronous audio and video connectivity with students and satisfy scheduling requirements at no expense for new facilities.

➤ *New Markets*

Online learning may reach domestic and foreign audiences which cannot easily be reached with other, more conventional modes of course, or the distribution of programs. The University of the South Pacific (USP) conveniently tap into study markets around the South Pacific with the development of online Foundation and Degree Biology courses. Thus, USP will enter a much greater market than other print distance courses and a far broader market than is achievable in a face-to-face course.

Online learning can support programming in an on-campus edition, which is hard to achieve viable figures. The University College of Kwantlen was willing to support the on-campus program. Classes grew as the same course was delivered at distance, and students examined commented that online delivery offered them greater freedom, and many said they could not take the course at the campus. Around the same moment, people cannot quit their jobs for many years of full-time study under economic hardship. Online graduates from a diverse variety of colleges and institutes, for example, ITT and Phoenix University give students the ability to their training when employed in their area of the industry at the same time.

Online courses will significantly reduce training costs for employees, especially if the company has remote sites. In addition to reducing rates of preparation, lower time is expended outside the workplace, reduced cost of administration, and higher efficiency. Most employee engagement initiatives at institutes follow this procedure. Staff is constantly improving their expertise by online learning. This provides great options to match progress in one's area when working.

➤ *International Partnerships*

International relationships are created with the aim of foreign markets. The students profit from the very varied existence of the students across collaborative aspects (international discussion groups and collaborative assignments). Furthermore, proximity to foreign experts is included in pedagogical opportunities related to international collaborations. That reviewed the effectiveness of a global initiative to promote collaborations in telecommunications technologies between the U.S. and foreign K12 classrooms. The project was focused on a conceptual structure that links knowledge and learning, technologies, and global relationships.

➤ *Reduced Time to Market*

The simplicity and pace at which course materials can be revised is a great help to online learning. During the revision of data that means retyping, printing, and binding, then emailing or distributing the content to students after a considerable wait. The tutor will update the relevant web pages during his lesson for an online course, upload new content, and it will be made accessible for pupils immediately. The delay is eliminated.

III. THE EMERGING ONLINE PEDAGOGY LEARNER

A socially intermediated online learning activity that underpins self-development and social interaction is now being challenged to the definition of the self-employed, place-bound, adult, self-motivated, disciplined, and objective-oriented student that characterized classical distance learners. According to Anderson and Garrison, "Individual methods for learning enabled by learning networks are the threat to individuality and alienation of the industrial age of distance education". Therefore, online learners must be ready to share their work, participate within small and wide communities in virtual environments, and cooperate the online learning or else face alienation in a world growing progressively reliant on networking and engagement.

Self-directed learning is another important feature of the online learner which leads from the classical distance learner profile. Self-directed learning can be defined as the ability to learn from myself or to be conscious of one's learning [8]. Students must have "self" conduct such as self-control, self-monitoring, initiative, and self-management, which are characteristics of self-governed or self-directed learning in online learning environments [9]. Since a teacher

is physically absent from online instruction, learners have the right to track and control their learning.

In addition, online learners can consider and appreciate resources for learning that can be effectively and constructively used by collaborative and communication technology. Some students are attracted to peer interactions or cooperation, while others must appreciate the educational importance of certain pedagogical structures. The interaction may be defined inherently as an interpersonal distinction that is pointed to as a need for association in the literature. The need for the association may be translated in the online learning setting as the connection or membership to supporting groups [10].

Research shows that online learners have important skills in organizational and communications and the fluid application of online learning technology [11]. Williams finds that organizational and communication abilities (including skills in writing) have controlled the top 10 general skills across all aspects in Internet-supported distance learning programs. The online learner is characterized by Powell as being "very comfortable in writing communications and slightly knowledgeable in web technology and competent in computing". That is a lack of knowledge and skill in using online learning technology, particularly communications and collaborative technologies, could present obstacles to student learning in online learning environments.

One illustration of how membership needs can be used in online learning environments is a network of experience. It is members realize that there is a social mind at work and that intelligence is common human capital. It is a pedagogical paradigm focused on a learning philosophy as a social phenomenon and applied by know-how networks, asynchronous learning networks, and other interactive and communicating Internet and Web-based technology [12][13].

Different types of online exercises were developed with Blackboard testing and assignment software for each course. It is very time-consuming to ask online fitness queries, but very advanced and usable. They are not only asynchronous and enable students to view them anywhere, but can have many tries, automatic saving, automatic corrections and randomization of queries, instructor input for individuals or groups, etc. There is a wide range of questions for teachers: fill in blanks, multiple ordering, choice, matching, short answer, real/false, essay, file answer, just to list any. In addition, the teachers and the students can conveniently connect photos, files (text/audio/video), and external links to the queries. That assignment was to pass the textbooks online with PowerPoint incorporated with photos, culture, grammar, and sounds notices in see Table 1. Audio and video were then produced or found as learning material or for work and activities via the Internet (e.g. YouTube). Electronic flashcards have been produced and are still common.

Table 1 Methods and Instruments Summary

Teaching Components		Methods / Tools
Lessons		PowerPoint
Electronic Flashcards (new words and phrases)		AUT Package
Lessons in Audio & Video		Recording & Filming Sources from YouTube
Individual Voice Recorder		Wimba Voice Board
Online Interactive Exercises		Blackboard Test/Assignment
Character-writing Movie Clips		Adobe Captivate (software)
Online Community	Mini Lectures	Elluminate Virtual Classroom
	Individual Blogs	Blog
	Virtual Drop-in	Elluminate Virtual Classroom
	Class Blog	Blog
	Pair/Group Work Corner	Elluminate / Wimba Voice Direct Conference / Wikis
	Email/Voicemail Centre	Email Voicemail
	Studio – for recording Paired/Group Oral Presentations	Wimba Voice Direct Conference
Class Podcast		Wimba Podcast
Assessment (assignments/oral Presentations)		Blackboard Test/Assignment Tools/Wimba Voice Tools / Elluminate / Wikis

IV. EFFECT ON LEARNERS

Online learning is facilitated by the exponential development of information technology. Teachers and scientists became incredibly involved in online learning to improve the performance of learners. As Lynch said, instructional information materials online learning and influences the lives of new learners, their teachers' lives, their friends, the culture, and the institution.

Online learning is a distance learning format that has long become an integral part of American education, which has been the biggest distance learning field in recent years [13][14]. Online learning is becoming the most common method of distance learning. In this research, that study is the background of learners in online learning and how it gives them benefits or drawbacks. As in Steam's post, online learning is one of the distance learning forms that teachers may use with any place. There are several types of distances: correspondence courses (performed over regular mailed with no interaction), television classes, CD (where students are statically informed contents), online learning (synchronous and/or asynchronous internet-based courses are offered), and mobile learning. There are many types of distance learning available today utilizing devices such as PDAs and cellular phones, a digital audio player like iPods or MP3 players).

Online learning is a fine way to distribute materials unbound by time or place, enabling the instruction to be accessible always. Students find the online world an easy way to suit their busy life with school. Some advantages are because some researchers use online instruction. Some of the key benefits of internet education include:

- Improved learning (enhanced comprehension of the content of classes, constructive conversation, focus on writing skills, technological abilities, and life skills, such as spell management, autonomy, and self-discipline).
- Interaction (increased the interaction between teachers and pupils, more involved students, and inactive students).
- innovative teaching (Online learning focussed on student centered where its increased variety and creativity of learning activities),
- Improved administration (time to review more thoroughly student work; capacity for online documenting and recording interaction; capacity to manage graduation online).
- savings (accommodating more students; enhanced student satisfaction).
- optimized physical resources (demand for campus infrastructure limits; reduced campus and parking congestion).
- Increased public access (Give students options; reach new student markets; appeal to current students thus increasing enrolments).

Questionnaire Students find online learning to be interesting in 80% of cases, with just 3% disagreeing. 65 percent of students say online learning classes are better than normal classes, although just 5% say they are not. The students react to "problems throughout and after online learning" 80 percent claimed it connected to the internet signal since most of them remain in the village. In a survey "The instructor gives a very brief and very small amount of tutorial, how to overcome it" 70 percent of students answer they need to explore to find the response to the teacher's information. And 65% of their teachers provide them input on their assignments in the last questionnaire: "Your instructor often provided feedback after you have sent video or task" in shown in table 2 [15]. The researchers believed that more advanced and autonomous students were ideal candidates for online learning.

Table 2 The Result of Students Questionnaire

S.no.	The questionnaire items	Student Result				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Online learning is interesting for you		3%	5%	80%	2%
2	Taking class online easier than a regular class		5%	30%	68%	10%
3	I always prepare myself before learning by making notes or record along the online learning process.			11%	85%	4%
4	Online learning practical for me			10%	90%	
5	The time of online learning for you, it is disturbing you, make you in hurry or. etc.		23%	70%	7%	
6	The cost that I should pay in online learning cheaper than you should go to campus		10%	15%	75%	
7	I always join the discussion about the topic of course		2%	20%	68%	10%
8	I felt active and confident with online learning			2%	78%	20%
9	I think high-quality learning can take place without interacting with teacher and students face-to-face		15%	25%	60%	
10	Interacting with teacher and students face-to-face			30%	70%	

V. IMPLICATIONS AND PROPOSALS

Online learning students need assistance to take an online course. The researcher proposes the following model as a guideline for a university conducting an online course. Figure 1 illustrates the proposed model and This analysis will take the following implications:

- The key obstacles facing students in online learning are technical difficulties and personal issues, supporting students to solve these issues will enhance satisfaction with the new learning style and encourage inspiration for online learning. Adequate and efficient internet access and 24-hour internet availability are also essential to solve technical problems.
- It is particularly necessary to draw up interesting and realistic online lessons and material. Enough lesson and exercise examples are also required. The nature and content of the study activities must also be assessed and reviewed sometimes.

- Online language learning strategies (OLLS) must be done before the training commences and after the course to promote encouragement for students to study online. In addition, interesting and inspiring guidance must be introduced at the outset of the course. In addition, the relationship between teachers and students must be enhanced so that students can take responsibility for their online learning and monitor it.
- Online student preparation should be assessed before the beginning of the course. Low-skilled English students must expect to cope with evolving learning modes. The assessment will involve student preference and preferred style, trust, ease and competence in Internet use and devices, desire to participate in self-direct learning, and intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.
- Online pedagogy learners require help to follow an online course. As a reference to a university delivering online training, the researcher proposes the following model. Figure 1 shows the proposed model:

Fig 1 Procedure to Improve Online Learning Course of Learning Process

VI. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This paper provides a review of the literature on online teaching course offerings have greatly improved the educational system over the past five years. For the last five years, online training offers have significantly improved the education sector and learning practices in teacher education. In total, 134 empirical studies were analysed. Online teaching and learning practices related to social, cognitive, and teaching presence were identified. The findings highlighted the need for a comprehensive view of the pedagogy of online education that integrates technology to support teaching and learning. The implications of this study for the development of online teaching and learning practices are discussed.

Marshall (2002) [16] studied on the "A sophistication paradigm for online learning". The authors believe that a process model is essential to promote the advancement of successful educational technological tools, irrespective of technical channels, organizational structures, and pedagogical frames. This article examines the importance of applying the current information engineering method model, called the Capability Maturity Model, to improve such a model. The document provides an outline of the CMM and addresses its potential use in the online learning sector. It considers two potential uses for its use: as a guide for improving online-learning acceptance and as a guide for online-learning operational incorporation. The article ends by discussing the potential value and preconditions of utilizing an adapted online-learning CMM version.

Fell (2003) [17] studied on the "First pedagogy, second technology: teaching and learning Online literacy of knowledge." This paper explains pedagogical and technological questions, difficulties, and results in designing an online course for knowledge literacy. The goal of this project is to optimize access for students to advanced information recovery skills and achieve the university's agile distribution and online education objectives. Online represents the successful combination of teaching and learning philosophy, instructional practices, and technical applications such that the learning results of campus and online students are ensured similarly.

Amirian (2003) [18] studied on the "Pedagogy & Videoconferencing: Recent Literature Review". According to the paper, the strongest approach to promote effective teaching practice might not be utilizing technology for technology-sake. This perspective by emphasizing that most of today's online-learning programs consist of easy converting information from the classroom to an interactive medium while maintaining its conventional, knowledge. In this case, too much emphasis is usually on 'classroom management and too little on learners, when a faculty must have optimal opportunities for learning and encourage self-reliance and analytical thought. The use of cognitive techniques at higher levels to exploit the web's dispersed structure is also uncommon.

Mehanna (2004) [19] studied "Online research pedagogies". The author says that it is essential that online-learning contexts and pedagogical evaluations of online experiences and conversations should be examined empirically. Part of the results of a multi-case analysis that studied four separate post-graduate programs online in four different U.K. universities is published in this article. From the one year of grounded studies, a paradigm of 29 pedagogical conduct was developed and 5 million words of online communications were analyzed. The results propose four pedagogic clusters that correspond with the grades of pupils but calculating the impact size shows a pedagogical value for everyone. The investigator proposed an online learning model.

Dabbagh (2005) [20] studied "Theory-based programming system" "Pedagogical models of online education". The author recommends a theory-based online-learning modelling approach emphasizing the transformational relationship between pedagogical frameworks, educational methods, and learning technology. The investigator explained that situate or dispersed cognition represents an apt fundamental information viewpoint that derives pedagogical models and structures for online education and provides a paradigm for theory-in-practice that characterizes and directs the design of online learning for the educational consequences of situated knowledge. There are specific instances of how this concept may be used in online learning environments. In this article, the theory-based online learning architecture was introduced which stresses the systemic and transformational relationship between pedagogical models, training techniques, and learning technology which thus enables the creator or the trainer to follow a sound design approach. In addition, it was submitted that recent developments in internet and web-based knowledge have led to the appearance of pedagogical patterns based on situational cognition and constructivist views of knowledge, which require the preconception of distance learning as an open and distributed learning environment that utilizes the Internet and web technology to support pedagogical tools. Incorporated by this new understanding of remote learning and the conceptualization framework characterizing the instructional effects of situated cognition, developers and instructors have the knowledge and tools to elaborate solutions and to organize, coordinate and deliberately distribute interactions to foster meaningful knowledge.

Conole (2008) [21] studied "Examination and usage of online-learning with the pedagogical paradigm". Any of the main pedagogical concepts and models, often mentioned during online learning, have been explored. 20 templates and frames are defined in this article. Thirteen of them are classified as being most supportive of associative, emotional, or situational learning prospects, 5 are general and two concerned evaluation practices. The investigator concluded that the structures and systems are used differently. It implies they are used in certain situations to direct the design phase (whether in education or a learning environment), and it is eventually seen, that the models and structures may often be seen as analytical instruments for

understanding the procedure. In some cases, they provide a 'pedagogical role' or alignment, and the study into curriculum design explores how templates and systems could be used to direct practitioners' practice and learning for students.

Hu & Grambling (2009) [22] to achieve online learning objectives, online learning strategies (OLSs) are described as the students' ability to recognize and handle their learning across a variety of cognitive, metacognitive, resource, and emotional strategies. Another contributing factor to online learner is like online learning.

Puri (2012) [23] studied on the "Executed online learning successfully considerations in pedagogy". This paper aims to define the teaching and learning principles that underlie successful online-Learning activities. The ideas that guide the good practice of teaching are pedagogical concepts. According to the reviewer, effective teaching or instructional practices are well described as far as online learning is concerned. The author has proposed five pedagogical parameters: material creation, storage and content management, packaging content, support from students, and evaluation. Online learning applies even to most pedagogical concepts applied to the conventional system of implementation. These standards can therefore be broadened to adapt to ensure swift technological improvements. The foundation of the use of features in LMS should be pedagogical concepts. Moreover, these concepts can be incorporated into the LMS as and function used comes with clear instructions for the proper way of using them to include pedagogically sound training. LMS suppliers also dispute each other. They argue on the one side that they can only provide online-learning instruments but cannot tell educators how to use these resources to teach. They argue, though, on the other hand, that they should provide "complete online learning options." Online learning cannot proceed without pedagogical methods, nor domain-relevant information being incorporated and taken into consideration.

Zammit, B. (2013) [24] studied on the "Pedagogical transition and core foundations: a case report". It focused on embedded techniques and cooperation between teaching personnel and diverse supporting areas at university in the ongoing implementation of curricula in a foundational unit at Victoria University, Melbourne, Australia. This paper addressed it also proposes that core base units play an important role in improving the experience of the first year.

Wei Li (2014) [25] studied on the "Reading Assignment Evaluation and Online Learning Assessments". This thesis was designed to review readings and evaluations in an online learning course at a research university in the United States. It is one of the basic courses in the online master's program in three credits. The thesis was attended by ten graduate students. Data is gathered for interviews and surveys. The findings revealed that participants did not complete reading tasks and had poor impressions of the contest style. There are discussed factors that have affected the completion of the lectures assigned. Based on the study

findings, important suggestions to improve reading and evaluation style for this online-learning course were made.

Khabbaz and Najjar's (2015) [26] study on the language acquisition practices of students has been explored in the Moodle language education curriculum. New technology in language learning, owing to the difficulties faced by the new technology, has been found to hinder independent learning. The meta-cognitive techniques were also less used and found to have a significant adverse effect on academic performance.

VII. CONCLUSION

Online teaching and learning are different, but at the same time, both are proven to work. Everyone can learn on the online platform. It can be proper knowledge and skills for effective online teaching. It must be innovative in educating the students to seek the best way. Online pedagogy is useful for learners, students, and teachers. It can learn at the house. Online study has affected the achievements of students. The new online educational environment of today requires that become those life-long learners that are acquainted with the new pedagogies for online teaching and the new technology required for facilitating online instruction. But they would also become better at evaluating and assessing student learning outcomes and their teaching content. One last thought, as educational leaders that are always teaching all students to become life-long learners. While they thought that conventional education and schooling were better, it was altered by technology. Teachers should constantly brace for evolving instructional methods. It has many advantages over conventional learning methods. Many students are drawn by this flexibility, even though they must use compensate for the internet. The course plan is different, depending on the content of the course itself, whether it is an on-campus or a distance course. Online Education has brought a positive impact on the lives of students and working professionals. It has allowed taking up extra courses along with their learners or job as per their convenience. If the professor would focus on the four areas presented here; technical/managerial presence, teaching presence, cognitive presence, and social presence, they would not only learn how to become great online professors. Elderly teachers use of overhead transparencies because naturally, they realized that showing a complex equipment photo in a lecture was pedagogically smarter than trying to explain it by words. One general conclusion is that perhaps not all resources must be used in an LMS kit, online or mixed learning courses.

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